

Contribution from the *Department of Computer Science, University of Pisa, Italy*—an IE member institution, rejoining in 2025 to continue its support for our mission.

AI as a Socio-Technical System: DETAILLS Living Lab for Sustainable Innovation

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20798730

Context and Objectives

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is rapidly reshaping societies, economies, and everyday life. More than a technical tool, it functions as a **socio-technical system** intertwined with human behaviour, institutions, and culture [1]. Addressing AI therefore requires moving beyond technical solutions toward participatory, interdisciplinary, and reflective approaches.

This perspective calls for new ways of designing, studying, and communicating AI: approaches that actively involve diverse stakeholders and foster collective understanding. **Living Lab methodologies** offer a promising response. First introduced as experimental environments to study technology in everyday contexts and later defined by ENoLL (European Networks of Living Labs) as user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on co-creation and real-life settings [2], Living Labs create spaces where users, researchers, and practitioners collaboratively explore, experiment, and co-design solutions, bridging the gap between innovation and societal needs.

Within this framework, the **Erasmus+ project DETAILLS** (DEsign Tools of Artificial Intelligence in Sustainability Living LabS) (<https://www.details.eu/>) brought together European universities and organisations to explore how AI-driven design methodologies can contribute to sustainability goals.

One of the most tangible results of the project has been the establishment of a **Living Lab in Pisa, Italy**, at one of the partner universities

involved in the Erasmus+ project. Its objective is to communicate AI as a socio-technical system and to explore its impacts through participatory, interactive, and interdisciplinary practices.

From Research to Design: Identifying Living Lab Practices

The design of the Pisa Living Lab was **grounded in a structured research phase** aimed at identifying effective Living Lab practices. Two complementary research activities informed our approach: a **systematic literature review** and a **validation workshop** with experts. For more in-depth information about the research phase, please refer to the documents “Living Lab Practices Desk Research” and “Workshop protocol for validating good practices in training activities” available for download here: <https://www.details.eu/results/>.

Literature Review on Living Lab Practices

The literature review identified key Living Labs practices from 154 documents in Scopus and Web of Science. It highlighted the importance of **participatory and multi-stakeholder approaches** to support inclusive and context-sensitive innovation.

It also emphasised **co-creation, experimentation, and iterative processes**, alongside the value of **interdisciplinary collaboration** for addressing complex challenges such as AI.

Finally, the review emphasised experiential and **project-based learning**, effective **stakeholder**

engagement, and the integration of **sustainability** and **systems thinking**. These principles informed the design of activities that combine learning, experimentation, and reflection in real-world contexts.

Validation Workshops on Good Practices

The validation workshops, involving 16 international experts, reinforced the importance of **experimental learning techniques** and **collaborative learning strategies**, particularly through prototyping and interdisciplinary teamwork.

They also emphasised **aligning skill development with industry needs**, especially by integrating AI, sustainability, and engagement with external organisations.

Overall, these research activities provided a solid foundation for translating theoretical principles into concrete practices. The insights gained directly shaped the structure and methodologies of the Pisa Living Lab, ensuring that its activities were both evidence-based and contextually relevant.

From Principles to Practice: DETAILLS Living Lab

Building on these insights, the **DETAILLS Living Lab in Pisa, Italy** (<https://share.google/7GxO9MYQaP05Xm18Y>) was designed as an open and collaborative environment where diverse stakeholders can engage with AI and its societal implications. The aim was not only to transfer knowledge but to create conditions for dialogue, experimentation, and co-creation.

The Living Lab brings together a wide community (researchers, students, companies, educators, artists, and citizens) reflecting the **multi-stakeholder approach** identified in the research phase. Activities have been organised into five main formats.

Talks provide structured moments of knowledge sharing, where experts address topics such as AI ethics, language and creativity,

and the social impacts of technology. These events are open to both academic audiences and the wider public, supporting dissemination while encouraging dialogue.

Thematic roundtables create horizontal spaces for discussion on issues such as AI and discrimination, gender and technology, and sustainability. Using participatory methods, these sessions enable open exchanges between academia and society, supporting collective sense-making and imagination.

Artistic events, including film screenings and live performances with AI, offer alternative perspectives on AI. By engaging creative communities, they expand the conversation beyond technical and academic domains, revealing how AI shapes cultural imaginaries and practices, and showcasing how artists experiment with and reinterpret AI through unconventional and alternative uses.

Training workshops focus on developing practical skills related to AI, including generative AI, trust in automation, and sustainability. These sessions rely on hands-on, experiential learning methods such as group work, case studies, and peer learning, with activities adapted to the specific contexts and needs of participants, directly reflecting the principles identified in the research phase.

Co-design workshops represent the most direct application of Living Lab methodologies. In these sessions, participants from different backgrounds work together on a shared project. Using approaches such as Design Thinking, Design Fiction, and prototyping, they collaboratively develop solutions that leverage AI. The project-based approach proved particularly effective in aligning diverse participants around common goals.

Through these interconnected activities, the Living Lab translates research principles into practice. It becomes a space where knowledge is not only shared but co-created and continuously refined.

Photos of activities organised by DETAILLS Living Lab in Pisa, Italy.

Reflections and Transferable Takeaways

The experience of designing and implementing the DETAILLS Living Lab offers several insights that may be transferable to other contexts.

A first lesson concerns **interdisciplinarity**. Working with AI requires integrating perspectives from multiple domains, as its impacts extend far beyond technology. Our experience showed that interdisciplinarity enriches both understanding and design processes. For example, discussions involving artists and citizens revealed perspectives that would not emerge in purely technical settings, highlighting alternative ways of thinking about AI and its uses.

However, interdisciplinarity also carries risks, particularly the tendency for discussions to remain at a superficial level. Addressing this requires creating opportunities for **deeper engagement** and **specialised learning**, especially in technically AI domains such as natural language processing and text analysis. In our experience, complementing Living Lab activities with more structured formats helps bridge this gap by combining methodological depth with hands-on engagement, as

exemplified by initiatives such as the annual summer school “Text Analysis and Large Language Models for Innovation Management” (<https://www.unipi.it/didattica/corsi/summer-schools/text-analysis-large-language-models-for-innovation-management/>).

A second insight relates to the value of **project-based approaches**. Co-design workshops demonstrated that working on shared, concrete problems helps align diverse participants and fosters collaboration. This approach proved particularly effective in bridging academia and industry, allowing participants to jointly explore how AI can address real-world challenges.

A further reflection concerns the relationship between understanding, imagination, and action. Given the complexity and rapid evolution of AI, participatory and interdisciplinary practices in Living Labs help develop a **shared understanding** of current challenges. This in turn enables **collective imagination**, the ability to envision shared, desirable futures grounded in diverse perspectives, which can ultimately **drive change**. As Sarah Housley argues, “a coherent and collective vision of achievable futures can inspire people to bring about change. These visions act as motivators and engines of imagination” [3].

References

[1] A.J.I. Jones, A. Artikis, J. Pitt, "The design of intelligent socio-technical systems", in *Artificial Intelligence Review*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 5-20, 2013.

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